

The Role of Human Resources in Interpreting the Relation between the Emphases on the Operations Standard and Improving the Overall Performance of the Palestinian Universities

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the role of human resources in interpreting the relationship between the standard of operations in the relationship between the focus on students and beneficiaries in achieving satisfaction of students in Palestinian universities. The study used the analytical descriptive method. The study was conducted on the university leadership in Al-Azhar, The study consisted of (416) individuals. The study sample consisted of (200) individuals, 182 of them responded, and the questionnaire was used in collecting the data. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which are: There is a statistically significant effect on the adoption of the standard of operations on improving the overall performance in Palestinian universities. "The value of the R Square (42.8%) indicates that (42.8%) of improvement in overall performance is due to the adoption of the standard of operations in universities Subject of study, there is a statistically significant impact on the adoption of the standard of operations on the development of human resources in the Palestinian universities. "The value of the R Square (64.5%) indicates that 64.5% of the adoption of the human resources criterion is due to the adoption by the Palestinian universities of the standard of operations. (50.1%) indicates that 50.1% of the improvement in overall performance is due to the adoption by the Palestinian universities of the criterion of interest in resources Humanity, there is a statistically significant effect of the adoption of the standard of operations on improving overall performance with the interest of human resources as an intermediary variable in Palestinian universities. "The role of human resources was revealed between adopting the standard of operations to improve overall performance. The study presented a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: the increasing focus of universities on human resources through the appropriate form to achieve the goals of the university on the one hand, and the workers on the other hand and in line with the approach of quality and excellence, the universities more attention to the management of operations through the design and development of academic programs The need for universities to plan performance improvement projects and implement them for all standards, especially the results criteria, the need for universities to invest in this good performance in obtaining the Data quality and excellence of international quality institutions, as it has a great impact on the reputation of the university, and what gives the university the momentum to continue improvement and improvement of the performance of the process.

Keywords: Human Resources, the Operations Standard, the Overall Performance, Palestinian Universities

1. INTRODUCTION

The system of quality and excellence in education at present is a feature of the age we live in embraces all aspects of the educational process such as curriculum, teacher, student, learning resources, university environment and university community, thus improving the efficiency of university performance and outputs.

As distinct universities design, manage, and improve operations in order to support their policy and strategy, they are fully satisfied to create value for employees, students and other stakeholders (EFQM, 2013). Through the development of the process design and management methodology, the improvement of processes in innovative ways to generate value for students and beneficiaries, the design of academic programs and the development of internal services according to the needs of students and beneficiaries.

The real tool and effective force in achieving the goals and objectives of organizations and the success of their operations are the human resources of highly skilled knowledge workers, and the management provides them with continuous development opportunities and training aimed at increasing their skills, investing their intellectual and cognitive abilities in performance development and empowering them always Empower from control the ability to work, freedom of movement, participation in responsibilities and decision-making. "Excellence Management" is essentially a distinct management of human resources (Al Shobaki et al., 2019).

And distinguished universities manage the knowledge and potential of their employees and develop them at the individual level, the level of work teams, and the university level, and interested in communication, reward and appreciation of their employees in a way that motivates them

and develop their loyalty to use their skills and knowledge for the benefit of the University (EFQM, 2013), (Al shobaki et al., 2018).

Therefore, there is a need for conditions that help university employees develop their performance by working as a team, and taking risks to meet the needs and desires of beneficiaries and stakeholders. Human resources management should contribute to the creation of individuals to change towards excellence and continuous improvement. This approach in performance to the success of its application, and requires clear and intensive communication to explain the reasons for change and justification and the extent of its impact on workers.

Based on the above, this study is one of the few studies aimed at answering the following main question: "What is the role of human resources in interpreting the relation between the standard of operations and improving the overall performance of Palestinian universities?"

Q1-: Is there an impact of adopting the standard of operations on improving overall performance in Palestinian universities?

Q2-: Is there an impact on the adoption of the standard of operations on the interest of human resources in Palestinian universities?

Q3-: Is there an impact on human resources to improve overall performance in Palestinian universities?

Q4-: Is there an impact on the adoption of the standard of operations on improving the overall performance of human resources as an intermediate variable in Palestinian universities?

2. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of the study is shown by the benefit that will be given to:

1. To provide Palestinian universities with the availability of the standard of operations management in their activities.
2. To provide Palestinian universities with the availability of a standard of focus on human resources as one of the criteria of international excellence
3. Identify the results of the overall performance in universities.
4. To provide recommendations and proposals documented and derived from the field study to help senior management of Palestinian universities in the application of excellence.
5. This study may contribute to drawing the attention of researchers to carry out many studies and researches in modern administrative curricula and apply them to vital sectors such as the higher education sector.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

In line with the study's questions, the current study seeks to achieve a set of objectives, namely:

1. Contribute to the recognition of the degree of adoption of the standard of operations, attention to human

resources, and the overall performance level in Palestinian universities.

2. Disclosure of the impact of adopting the standard of operations on improving overall performance in Palestinian universities.
3. Know the effect of adopting the standard of operations on the interest of human resources in Palestinian universities.
4. Identify the impact of attention on human resources on improving overall performance in Palestinian universities.
5. Contribute to the detection of the role of human resource mediators in interpreting the impact of adopting the standard of operations on improving the overall performance in Palestinian universities.

4. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Ho 1: There is a statistically significant effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to adopt the standard of operations to improve the overall performance in the Palestinian universities.

Ho 2: There is a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to adopt the standard of operations on the development of human resources in the Palestinian universities.

Ho 3: There is a statistically significant effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level of interest in human resources on improving overall performance in Palestinian universities.

Ho 4: There is a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to adopt the standard of operations to improve the overall performance with the concern of human resources as an intermediate variable in the Palestinian universities.

5. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

First - operations standard:

Distinguished universities design, manage, and improve operations in order to support their policy and strategy, with full satisfaction to create value for employees, students and other stakeholders.

This criterion consists of the following sub-criteria:

A. Process design and management methodology, through:

1. Identify and design the necessary processes to implement the university policy and strategy and achieve its objectives.
2. University interest in completing the work according to the comprehensive quality systems and standard specifications.
3. Clearly define the powers and responsibilities when the operations are completed.

B. Improve processes in innovative ways to generate value for students and beneficiaries through:

1. Develop new processes, teaching methods, and new university administration.
2. Encouraging the university to creatively innovate in the quality and diversity of services provided.

3. Motivate innovative creative talents for employees, students and stakeholders to help with new improvements.

C. Design academic programs and develop internal services according to students' needs through:

1. Use market research and student questionnaires to identify needs and perceptions of the current situation.
2. Design and develop new specialties as needed: students, beneficiaries and employers.
3. Predict the impact of modern technology on the development of new specialties.
4. Use creativity and innovation in developing new teaching styles and services.

Second - Human resources:

Human resources management is the body that handles the most efficient use of human resources at all levels in the organization in order to contribute to achieving the objectives.

And distinguished universities manage the knowledge and potential of their employees and develop them at the individual level, the level of work teams and the university level, and interested in communication, reward and appreciation of their employees in a way that motivates them and develop their loyalty to use their skills and knowledge for the University.

This criterion consists of the following sub-criteria:

A. Human resources planning, management and improvement, through:

1. Develop strategies, policies and plans for human resources (employees) at the university.
2. Engage staff in the development of HR strategies, policies and plans.
3. The human resource policies and organizational structure of the University are consistent with the University's policy and strategy.

B. Determine the continuity and development of knowledge and qualifications of human resources, through:

1. Develop staff development and training plans, and use them to ensure that their abilities meet the university's current and future needs.
2. Develop, mentor and train staff to help them realize their full potential.
3. Assist staff in improving their performance through assessments and other activities.

C. Share and empower human resources through:

1. Enforce adequate staff powers and enable them to complete their work assignments.
2. Provide opportunities that stimulate interaction and support creativity and there is positive behavior among staff at all levels in the university.
3. Encourage employees to work with each other within teams in one field.

D. Reward, appreciation and attention to human resources at the University, through:

1. Estimate individuals to encourage, empower and sustain their interaction.
2. Provide the University with appropriate levels of employment benefits (retirement, savings, and health insurance).
3. Provide resources and services that meet or exceed systems and labor laws for human resources development.

Third - Overall performance:

Where distinguished universities measure and comprehensively achieve outstanding results in their performance while respecting the key elements of their strategy and plans. This criterion consists of the following sub-criteria:

A. Results of financial performance, such as:

1. The University's commitment to spending according to the financial budget items.
2. Rationalize the University for its Expenses.
3. Achieving the University's financial surplus resulting from its operations.
4. Collect university debts owed by beneficiaries.

B. Non-financial performance results, for example:

1. An increase in the number of students enrolled in the university.
2. A rise in the chances of university graduates in employment for other universities.
3. Distinguish the results of internal and external self-assessment.
4. Introducing the university to new programs constantly adapted to the labor market.

C. Overall performance indicators - internal university metrics for overall performance monitoring, eg:

1. Improvement in university performance.
2. Exploitation of buildings and facilities effectively.
3. Link the university with good relations with suppliers and partners.
4. Access to information and knowledge in the form, time and quantity appropriate.

Al-Tala '(2016) determined that the most important results of the impact of the emphasis on human resources on performance are as follows:

1. Increase employee satisfaction and organizational loyalty.
2. Improve individual and group performance at the university.
3. A positive regulatory climate.
4. Employees' sense of job security.
5. The quality of dealing with students and beneficiaries and meet their needs quickly.
6. Preserving university resources and rationalizing consumption.
7. Carrying workers for their social responsibility.

He also believes that the main results of the performance management impact on performance are as follows:

1. Distinguish in the university performance and in the results of internal and external evaluation.

2. Evolution in teaching methods and administrative processes.
3. The University achieves a financial surplus resulting from its operations.
4. An increase in the number of students enrolled in university.
5. Increase the number of new programs adapted to the needs of the labor market.
6. Higher opportunities for university graduates in employment compared to other universities.
7. Reduce costs through the use of modern technology.
8. Increase productivity and improve employee performance.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Study of (El Talla et al., 2019) aimed at identifying the intermediate role of applying the criterion of focus on human resources in the relationship between adopting the leadership standard in the international models of quality and achieving job satisfaction among the workers in the Palestinian universities. The study used the analytical descriptive method. The study was conducted on the university leadership in (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University, Al-Aqsa University), the study population consisted of (416) individuals. The study sample consisted of (200) individuals, 182 of whom responded, and the questionnaire was used in collecting the data. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is: The level of Palestinian universities' adoption of the criterion of concentration on human resources got a high degree to some extent. The level of job satisfaction among the workers in the Palestinian universities studied was high due to the statistically significant effect of the leadership criterion on employee satisfaction. The focus on human resources, the existence of a statistically significant impact on the adoption of the criterion of concentration on human resources to achieve job satisfaction in Palestinian universities, the standard focus on human resources partly mediated the relationship between adopting the standard of leadership and achieving job satisfaction for Palestinian universities' employees. The study presented a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: increasing interest in the application of the leadership criterion as a basic guide for excellence in universities, the development of human resources in universities and increasing the focus on them; work on creating job satisfaction among university employees by creating a positive atmosphere and providing them with material and moral motivation.
- Study of (Al Shobaki et al., 2019) aimed to identify the intermediate role of knowledge and information management in the relationship between adopting the strategy criterion and improving the overall performance. The study used descriptive analytical method. The study was conducted on the university

leadership in Al-Azhar, Islamic and Al-Aqsa Universities. The study population consisted of (416) individuals and sample study consisted of the (200) individuals (182) individuals responded, and the questionnaire was used in the collection of data. The study reached a number of results, the most important of which were: The level of adoption by the Palestinian universities of the strategy criterion was very high. The level of adoption by the Palestinian universities of the knowledge and information management standard was very high. The overall performance level in the Palestinian universities under study was significant. The overall performance of the universities has a statistically significant impact on the adoption of the strategy criterion on knowledge and information management. There is a statistically significant impact of the adoption of knowledge and information management on improving overall performance in Palestinian universities. This information partially mediates the relationship between adopting the strategy standard and improving overall performance in Palestinian universities. The study presented a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: Greater attention to the application of the strategy criterion as a basic guide for excellence in universities. Developing information systems in universities and improving the mechanism of information exchange and knowledge. Work on developing the overall performance of universities through adopting international excellence models.

- Study of (Al Shobaki et al., 2018) aimed to identify the performance of the administrative staff in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire distributed randomly to the sample of 320 administrative staff from the three universities. The response rate was (81.87%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high level of performance from the point of view of the administrative staff, as the percentage reached (81.51%). The results showed that there were no differences in the perception of the employees according to the variables "age, years of service, job level (manager, head of department, administrative, Workplace". The results showed that there are differences in the perception of employees to perform the function depending on the university variable, where the results indicated that there are statistically significant differences between the Islamic University and Al-Aqsa University in the job performance in favor of the Islamic University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the three Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip should give special attention to job performance in general and Al-Aqsa University and Al-Azhar University in particular. The Employees of universities should have the opportunity

to participate in decision-making. The Management of the three universities should keep interest in continuous improvement of the performance of their employees. Enhancing the periodic evaluation of the job performance, informing employees about their evaluations, and giving them the chance to express their opinion about it. Solving employees' problems and giving them the opportunity to contribute in solving their own problems. And the use of the staff rotation method periodically.

- Study of (Almasri et al., 2018) aimed to study The Organizational Structure and its role in applying the Information Technology Used the Palestinian universities as a comparative study between Al-Azhar and Islamic universities. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire that randomly distributed among Palestinian university workers in Gaza Strip. A sample of (182) administrative staff from the two universities, the response rate was (81.35%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high level of the Information Technology Used from the perspective of administrative staff, there is a direct correlation between The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used, the role and impact of The Organizational Structure in the nature of the Information Technology Used, the absence of differences between the sample according to the variable (gender and age), there are statistically significant differences in the perception of The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used according to the variable of scientific qualification in The Organizational Structure, while there were no differences in Field of the Information Technology Used, the differences in The Organizational Structure according to the scientific qualification were in favor of those who obtained the diploma degree compared to other practical qualifications, the absence of differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used depending on the variable years of service, the differences in The Organizational Structure and technology perception depending on the job level variable (Director, Head of Section, and Administrative Officer) for the benefit of the Administrative Officer, the absence of differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used depending on the workplace variable, the differences in the perception of employees The Organizational Structure and the Information Technology Used by the University working for the Islamic University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the managements of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip should be given more attention to the existing The Organizational Structure and

modified to suit the need of work, the need for universities to continue to pay attention to the continuous improvement of the Information Technology Used and strengthening the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empowering university staff.

- Study of (El Talla et al., 2018) the study was designed to identify the reality of applying the leadership standard in the international quality models in Palestinian universities. The study used the analytical descriptive method. The study was conducted on the university leadership in Al-Azhar and Islamic Universities. The study population consisted of 282 individuals. 119 individuals responded, and the questionnaire was used for data collection. The study has reached a number of results, the most important of which is the existence of a high level of results of university performance in the Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorate in the following order: performance results for students and beneficiaries, performance outcomes in relation to society and finally: performance results in relation to human resources. The study presented a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: increasing the interest of universities in the university staff by providing them with job security and increasing their participation in decision making, increasing the interest of the local community through activating the continuing education departments and partnerships with the private sector, increasing the interest of students and beneficiaries by providing an educational environment and appropriate learning and academic programs that meet the needs of the labor market.
- Study of (FarajAllah et al., 2018) aimed to know the relationship between the nature of the work and the type of communication among the Employees in the Palestinian universities. A comparative study between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire that is randomly distributed among the employees of Al-Azhar and Al-Aqsa universities in Gaza Strip. The study was conducted on a sample of (176) administrative employees from the surveyed universities. The response rate was (85.79%). The study reached a number of results, the most important of which is that there is a high degree of satisfaction with the nature of work prevailing in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage was (68.15%). There is a Mean level of communication from the point of view of administrative staff, with a percentage of (67.50%). There is a direct correlation between the nature of the work and the prevailing pattern of communication. There is an absence of differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the nature of work and the prevailing pattern of communication. There is an

absence of differences in the perception of Employees nature of work and the pattern of communication prevailing depending on the variables (age, years of service, job level, and university). There are statistically significant differences between Al-Azhar University and Al-Aqsa University in favor of Al-Azhar University. The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the management of the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip in general, and Al-Aqsa and Al-Azhar Universities in particular should be provided with a good nature of work and communication. There is a need for continuing the management of universities to pay attention and continuous improvement of the performance of employees. There is an importance of solving the problems of Employees and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems. Staff rotation should be used periodically and the need to strengthen the democratic the dominant pattern of leadership and empower university Employees.

- Study of (Madi et al., 2018) aimed to identify The Organizational Structure and its impact on the dominant pattern of leadership in the Palestinian university in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive method through a questionnaire randomly distributed among Palestinian university Employees in Gaza Strip. The study was conducted on a sample of (320) administrative staff from the three universities. The required sample calculated according to the law (274) Employees, and the response rate was (81.87%). The study found that there is a high degree of satisfaction with the nature of The Organizational Structure in the Palestinian universities in Gaza Strip from the point of view of the administrative staff, which reached (68.05%). The results showed that there was a Mean level of participation of decision-makers, with a percentage of (64.91%). There is a direct correlation between the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision makers. There is a significant impact of The Organizational Structure on the participation of decision makers. There is absence of differences between the sample according to the gender variable in their perception of the nature of The Organizational Structure and the extent of participation of decision-makers. There is absence of differences in the perception of Employees to the nature of The Organizational Structure and the participation of decision-making Employees depending on the age variable. There are statistically Sig. differences according to the variable of scientific qualification in The Organizational Structure, while there were no differences in the extent of participation of decision-making personnel.
- Study of (Abu Sultan et al., 2018) aimed to identify the Dominant Pattern of Leadership and its role in determining the type of administrative communication at

the Islamic University. The researchers used the method of Stratified random sampling in the study. The study was conducted on a sample of 144 administrative staff from the Islamic University of Gaza. The response rate was 77.08%. The study found that there is a high degree of satisfaction with The Style of Leadership in the Islamic University - Gaza from the point of view of the administrative staff, where the percentage reached (73.52%). There is a high degree of satisfaction with the pattern of communication prevailing in the Islamic University- Gaza from the point of view of administrative staff, where the percentage (76.52%). There is a direct correlation between The Style of Leadership and communication pattern, the role of The Style of Leadership in determining the type of administrative communication at the Islamic University- Gaza. There are no differences in the perception of workers in the pattern of communication while there are differences in The Style of Leadership according to the age variable in favor of the lower age groups. There are no statistically significant differences in the perception of the leadership pattern according to the variable (gender, qualification) and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of The Style of Leadership and style of communication depending on the variable years of service, and the absence of differences in the perception of the employees of The Style of Leadership and style of communication depending on the level of career variable (manager, head of department, administrative officer). The study reached a number of recommendations, the most important of which is that the interest of the departments of the Palestinian universities and the Islamic University should be increased in order to provide and maintain a good The Style of Leadership, the need to improve the existing communication pattern at the university and to give universities the opportunity to participate in decision-making, the importance of solving the problems of workers and giving them the opportunity to contribute to solving their own problems. The need to use the method of rotation of employees and periodically, and the importance of promoting democratic leadership and empowerment of university staff.

- Study of (El Talla, 2017) aimed to investigate the relationship between the organizational variables and job performance at Gaza strip Universities, the organizational variables included: communication style, nature of work, the technology used. And it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant in employees trends toward the reality of organizational variables attributed to some characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a questionnaire consisting of (50) paragraphs. The questionnaire was distributed randomly to (320) employees of the administrative staff in Gaza strip

universities; (262) employees responded, and the results showed the availability of a high degree of organizational variables in Gaza Universities, the order of variables were as follows: the technology used, the nature of work, and finally communication style, and it showed a high level of job performance, in addition the results showed a significant correlation between organizational variables and job performance, and there was existence of differences in the perception of the organizational variables depending on the university, for the benefit of the Islamic university, and differences between AlAzhar University and Alaqsa University for the benefit of Al-Azhar University, as results showed no differences between the sample depending on the variables: the functional level and the workplace .
Keywords: organizational variables, communication style, work nature, used technology, job performance.

- Study of (El Talla, 2015) aimed to investigate the reality of the burnout among Gaza electricity distribution company workers, which included burnout dimensions: Emotional exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Personal accomplishment. And aimed to the organizational causes of burnout, and it aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant trends in working toward the reality of burnout attributed to some demographic and organizational characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) consisting of (22) items. And the questionnaire of organizational causes of burnout consisting of (31) items. The questionnaires were distributed randomly to (69) worker, the results showed that the availability of a medium degree of burnout in the company, and that there is high availability of Emotional exhaustion scope, average degree for Depersonalization scope and low degree of Personal accomplishment scope. Also the results showed the existence of organizational causes for burnout among workers with the exception of the area of social relations, which was moderately and was the order of the causes are as follows (the weakness of physical stimulation, the limited powers of the work, work stress, conflict of values, poor social relationships). The results showed no differences between the samples due to the variables of gender, age, and years of service in their perception of burnout. The researcher recommended the company to work on treatment the causes of burnout, and increase the attention to workers.
- Study of (Smulowitz, 2015) aimed at identifying the potential impact of performance indicators on the perceived outcome of organizational change to understand differences in stakeholder views. The data were collected by interviewing 32 participants from four departments to support educational services and a group of senior Leadership University. The results indicated that the two implementers failed to assess employee

satisfaction, contribute to the implementation process, and performance indicators can be the main vision for successful change efforts.

- Study of (Moradzadeh, 2015), which aimed to identify the feasibility of applying the European model of excellence in higher education institutions. The descriptive method was used in the study. The data were collected from 22 educational zones through a random sample of (345), Middle, managers and staff, in all educational units. The results showed that the institutions of higher education under study applied well the elements of the European model of excellence, and that three main elements influencing the implementation of the criteria of the European model of excellence are the stakeholders, leadership and structure. The results also showed the need to develop a model that takes into account the local culture and other environmental factors and that standards of enterprise enable the results of beneficiaries, employee outcomes, community outcomes, and key performance outcomes.
- Study of (El Talla, 2014) aimed to investigate the reality of the organizational climate for administrator's staff at Al-Azhar University - Gaza, which included some elements of the organizational climate such as: organizational structure, the dominant pattern of leadership and the extent of participation of workers in decision-making. It aimed to identify the extent of differences statistically significant trends in working toward the reality of organizational climate attributed to some demographic and organizational characteristics of the study population. The data has been collecting using a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed at random-layer sample to (77) male and female employees of the administrative staff in the university; The results showed that the availability of a medium degree of organizational climate at the Al-Azhar University with percentage (66.64 %), and that there is availability of the average for all scopes of organizational climate, with the exception of the dominant pattern of leadership which its degree was high. The orders of scopes were as the following: the dominant pattern of leadership , the organizational structure , and finally the extent of participation of workers in decision-making. The results showed no differences between the samples due to the variables of gender, age, years of service in their perception of organizational climate, while there are significant differences in the perception of the reality of organizational climate depending on the variable qualification in the areas of (organizational structure, the extent of participation in decision-making and in the total scope of organizational climate); and that differences were in favor of holding a diploma, the differences did not exist in the scope the dominant pattern of leadership .

- Study of (Shirvani et al., 2011), which aimed at evaluating the performance of medical science universities based on the European model of excellence. This study was conducted between 2012 and 2011. The study was applied to a sample of 13 universities. The educational work of the nine standards of the model by a radar methodology through the managers who received the training. The results showed that all universities scored higher than 200/1000, while one university obtained 350/1000, and that the differences between the quality criteria and the performance results were between 19.4 and 102.5. The main performance results were higher and the results of the society the results indicated that there are no significant differences between the results and the possibilities and the nine criteria of the model according to the university variable. The study recommended that the Iranian medical universities plan and implement improvement projects for all standards, especially the results criteria.
- Study of (Adel, 2009) aimed at identifying the most important factors that lead to higher performance of Egyptian higher education institutions, achieving distinct results, identifying strengths and areas that need improvement to achieve sustainable excellence, and using questionnaire to collect data. The study found that the Egyptian higher education institutions have substantial potential (leadership, personnel, strategy, resources, partnership, and processes) that directly affect their results (employee satisfaction, user satisfaction, impact on society, and performance outcomes). Will improve the overall excellence of Egyptian higher education institutions.

Methodology of the study:

The study method: Based on the nature of the study and the objectives that it sought to achieve, the study used

descriptive analytical method, which depends on the study of the phenomenon as it exists in reality and is concerned as a precise description and expressed in qualitative and quantitative terms. The qualitative expression describes the phenomenon and explains its characteristics. Quantitative expression gives us a numerical description shows the amount or size of this phenomenon and its degree of correlation with other phenomena.

Study Society: The study population consists of all academic staff holding managerial positions in the Palestinian universities under study (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University, Al-Aqsa University).

Sample of the study: The sample of the study was selected using the method of class randomization as one of the statistical methods used to be representative of the study society in accordance with the rules of scientific research in the selection of samples. The sample size (127) was one of the study society. The questionnaires were distributed manually. A statistical sample of (27) samples was selected from outside the study sample. Statistical analysis was conducted to verify the validity and stability of the questionnaire.

The characteristics of the study sample: The statistical frequencies were used to determine the characteristics of the sample of the study and the field data were collected through them in order to identify their characteristics in terms of scientific, practical and social structure. These characteristics represent variables that may affect the results of this study later, their change may also affect the results of similar studies if applied to the same community of the study, and the result of this study was taken as a check of their results. These are the recurrent distributions of employee data and corporate data.

Table 1: Distribution of the sample of the study

Job title	Dean and above	Deputy Dean	Head of Academic Section	Manager	Head of Administrative Section	Total
Number of duplicates	34	19	43	4	3	103
Percentage	33 %	18.4 %	41.7 %	3.9 %	2.9 %	100 %
Qualification	Ph.D.	M.A.	BA			Total
Number of duplicates	91	10	2			103
Percentage	88.3 %	9.7 %	1.9 %			100 %
Years of service	Less than 5 years	5-10 years	11-15 years	15years and over		Total
Number of duplicates	3	17	19	64		103
Percentage	2.9 %	16.5 %	18.4 %	62.1 %		100 %
Age	Less than 35 years	45-36years	56-45years	55 years and over		Total
Number of duplicates	4	30	56	13		103

Percentage	3.9 %	29.1 %	54.4 %	12.6 %		100 %
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Study tool:

To achieve the objective of the study, the current study was used as a study tool in the collection of data related to the subject of the study, which was prepared and developed based on the criteria used by the researchers in the literature and previous studies. The questionnaire appeared in three fields: (10) paragraphs, and the field of human resources development and be of (12) paragraph, the field of total performance may be of (12) paragraph, and the questionnaire was presented to a group of arbitrators with the competence to guide their views on the adequacy of paragraphs of the questionnaire for the purpose of ensuring correctness of the sound Language and its clarity. The five-point Likert scale is used to mean the degree of improvement (very large - 5 degrees, large - 4 degrees, medium - 3 degrees, low - 2 degrees, very low - one degree).

Statistical Processes:

The statistical package of Social Sciences (SPSS) was used. Macro Process v2.15 was also used. The following statistical methods were used: percentages, frequencies, arithmetic mean, Cronbach's Alpha test,), Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, Pearson Correlation Coefficient, T-test, Simple Linear Regression, Multiple Regression, Path Analysis.

Believe the study tool:

The validity of the study instrument was verified by using the internal consistency method to measure the correlation strength between the scores of each area of the field with the total score of the field to which it belongs. The results indicated that the first field, the "operations standard" was directly correlated with all the paragraphs it measured, the correlation between (0.696 - 0.933), and the second field "attention to human resources" is directly correlated with all the paragraphs that measure it. The correlation coefficients ranged from (0.548 - 0.910), while the third area "total performance" is directly correlated with all paragraphs Measured, correlation coefficients ranged (0.349 - 0.879), all of which are statistically significant (0.01 = α), indicating the correlation of the first area of the field, which means that it is internally consistent with the field you measure,

Table 4: Results of analysis of the basic dimensions of the study

No.	Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	%
1.	Standard operations	3.614	0.732	8.513	0.000	72.27 %
2.	Attention to human resources	3.601	0.705	8.649	0.000	72.02 %
3.	Overall performance	3.638	0.626	10.338	0.000	72.76 %

It is clear from the previous table that the level of adoption by the Palestinian universities for the standard of operations came to a great extent, with an average of 3.614 and a percentage of 72.27%. The standard deviation indicates that the respondents' responses were not significantly different and were close to their arithmetic mean, (0.732). The level of adoption by Palestinian universities for the criterion of interest reached a medium level. The mean was 3.601 and 72.02%. The standard deviation indicates that the

Stability of the study instrument: The stability of the study questionnaire was verified through the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. The results shown in the previous table indicate that the value of the Cronbach alpha coefficient was high for all areas of the study instrument, ranging from (0.930 to 0.957). The value of the Alpha Cronbach coefficient between (0-1) and the closer to the one indicated the existence of high stability and the closer to zero indicated the lack of stability, which means that the questionnaire has a high stability.

Table 2: Stability of the study instrument

No.	Dimension	No. Of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1.	Standard operations	10	0.957
2.	Attention to human resources	12	0.930
3.	Overall performance	12	0.935

Natural distribution test (Kulmgrove-Smernov test)

The researchers used the Kulmgrove-Smarnoff test to determine whether the data follow normal distribution or not, a necessary test in the case of hypothesis testing, since most laboratory tests require that data be distributed naturally. Table (3) shows the results of the test where it was found that the value of the level of significance for each field is greater than 0.05 (sig.> 0.05). This indicates that the data follow the normal distribution and the scientific tests should be used.

Table 3: Normal distribution test

No.	Dimension	Sig.
1.	Standard operations	0.643
2.	Attention to human resources	0.895
3.	Overall performance	0.711

Answer the study questions and test hypotheses:

Answer to the study questions: The main axes of the study were analyzed by calculating the arithmetic averages, percentages and T test of the sample per axis.

respondents' responses were not significantly different and were close to their arithmetic mean. The deviation is (0.705). Finally, the results showed that the overall performance level in the Palestinian universities studied was very high. The mean was 3.638 and the percentage was 72.76%. The standard deviation indicates that the respondents' response was not very different and was close to and the mean deviation was (0.266).

TEST HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

In order to test hypotheses (I, II, and III), simple linear regression was performed. The F test was used to identify the significance of the model as a whole. The ability of the model to interpret the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables was used. For Beta parameters, it was used to determine the expected change in the dependent variable Because of the change in one unit of the independent variable. The data were also confirmed to be suitable for the regression analysis assumptions by the absence of a multiple linear correlation between the independent variables "Multi-Collinearity" given the variance inflation factor (VIF) and Tolerance test for the independent variables, Problems with high correlation between independent variables.

Firstly- As a result of the first hypothesis, which states that "there is a significant statistical effect at the level (0.05 α) to adopt the standard of operations to improve the overall performance in Palestinian universities."

The results shown in Table (5) revealed that the value of (F) for the full model was (75.475) and the probability value (0.000) which is a statistically significant value at (0.05) indicating the significance of the model as a whole. (42.8%), indicating that (42.8%) of the improvement in the overall performance is due to the adoption of the standard of operations in the universities in question and the rest is due to other variables that affect the overall performance, and the value of the coefficient The correlation of the model was (0.654) indicating a strong positive relationship.

Table 5: Result of the first hypothesis test

Dimension	Overall performance		
	Beta	T- Test	Sig.
Processes	0.560	8.688	0.000
R	R Square	F Change	Sig. F Change
0.654	0.428	75.475	0.000

And the value of the (Beta) was (0.560), the value of (T-Test) was (8.688) and the value of statistical significance Sig (0.000) which is a statistical value at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and from the former can accept the first hypothesis: "There is a statistically significant effect at ($\alpha = 0.05$) to adopt the standard of operations to improve overall performance in Palestinian universities." This is due to the fact that universities are developing their operations more and more in line with international quality standards. TQM focuses on operations, not on outputs only, and as the University's operations and academic programs are strong and the needs of students and beneficiaries are met, The results of university performance, the university gained good reputation, and the number of enrolled.

This finding was agreed with Calvo-Mora & Roldan (2006), which showed that leadership leads to the development of excellence in results across operations. And studies by: (Calvo-Mora & Roldán: 2006), (Adel, 2009), Moradzadeh: 2015) which showed a significant relationship between processes and the results of university performance.

The relationship between processes and performance results is logical and natural. The more the university performs its operations distinctly, through: a clear methodology for designing and managing operations, improving its processes

in creative ways that generate added value for students and beneficiaries, and design academic programs and services as needed by students, It is expected and expected that the results of performance will be distinct, whether the results of students and beneficiaries, or workers, or society, and also at the level of overall performance results. The TQM approach is a holistic approach that focuses not only on outputs but on all stages of the system. Inputs, processes and outputs.

Second- As a result of the second hypothesis, which states that "there is a significant statistical effect at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to adopt the standard of operations on the development of human resources in Palestinian universities."

The results shown in Table (6) revealed that the value of (F) of the full model was (183.321) and the probability value (0.000) which is statistically significant at (0.05) indicating the significance of the model as a whole. (64.5%), indicating that (64.5%) of the adoption of the criterion of focus on manpower is due to the adoption of the Palestinian universities to the standard of operations, and the rest due to other variables, and the value of correlation coefficient of the model amounted to (0.803) indicating a strong positive relationship.

Table 6: Result of the second hypothesis test

Dimension	Development of human resources		
	Beta	T- Test	Sig.
Processes	0.774	13.540	0.000
R	R Square	F Change	Sig. F Change

0.803	.6450	183.321	0.000
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As it reached the value of the coefficient of Beta (0.774), T-Test (13.540), and statistical significance (0.000). This is a statistically significant value at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The second hypothesis can be accepted: "There is a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to adopt the standard operations on the development of human resources in Palestinian universities. "The researchers argue that universities that wish to develop their operations need to develop their academic management staff to provide them with the opportunity to be able to manage and execute processes distinctly.

The results were consistent with 2009Adel (Moradzadeh: 2015) in high availability of human resources, with the view of workers, which indicated a medium degree of human resources results.

The results differed with Smulowitz (2015), with a low score in human resources results.

Third- As a result of the third hypothesis, which states that "there is a significant statistical effect at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the attention of human resources to improve the overall performance in Palestinian universities."

The results shown in Table (7) revealed that the value of (F) of the full model was (101,508), and the probability value (0.000) was a statistically significant value at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) indicating the significance of the whole model. (50.1%), indicating that (50.1%) improvement in overall performance was due to the adoption by Palestinian universities of the criterion of attention to human resources and the rest due to other variables. The correlation coefficient of the model was (0.708) Demonstrating a strong positive relationship.

Table 7: Result of the third hypothesis test

Dimension	Overall performance		
	Beta	T- Test	Sig.
HR	0.628	10.075	0.000
R	R Square	F Change	Sig. F Change
0.708	0.501	101.508	0.000

And the value of the (Beta) (0.628, and the value of (T-Test) (10.075) and the value of the statistical significance Sig (0.000) which is a statistical value at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), and from the former can accept the third hypothesis: "There is a statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the attention of human resources to improve the overall performance in Palestinian universities." The researchers attributed this to the fact that the efforts of the universities in the attention and development of workers and the satisfaction of stakeholders, Non-financial, requires universities, and through their leaders and employees, to do more to improve this performance and improvement touch Over him, leading to the degree of excellence, and this is in line with what referred to (Shirvani et al) of the need for universities planning improvement projects and the implementation of all standards and criteria for special results.

This indicates that the results of the overall performance in the universities under study are good and compatible with the development of human resources in universities, and in a manner appropriate to achieve the goals of universities, and in line with the approach of quality and excellence.

The result was agreed with the studies of: (2009), Badri & Selim (2006) and Badri & Selim (2006), which showed a relationship between the focus on human resources and the results of university performance.

The researchers believe that human resources in universities, composed of academics with the highest scientific degrees, contributors to the scientific research process, and administrators working in an auxiliary environment and

complementary to the academic and research process, constitute the internal client of the university and one of the parties to the learning process. Students and beneficiaries, and provide services to the community, the labor market, and thus contribute to the differentiation of the results of university performance.

This is confirmed by El Talla et al. (2019). He believes that excellence in performance comes from the excellence in knowledge possessed by human resources, which is the focus of the work of the organizations, and it is more than just doing the work well, it concerns the workers who work and commit themselves to carrying out the tasks entrusted to them on an exceptional basis.

Fourthly- The result of the fourth hypothesis, which states that "there is a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to adopt the criterion of operations to improve the overall performance of the existence of interest in human resources as a mediator variable in Palestinian universities."

In order to detect the intermediary role of human resources between the adoption of the standard of operations to improve the overall performance was used Path analysis, where the initial verification of some preconditions to test the role of the mediator of the variable, which is the significance tests for the three previous hypotheses, Of its significance as it indicated all tests as a statistical function at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

After checking the previous conditions, the overall effect on the model is divided into two main parts that can be presented as follows: 1) Direct effect of the independent

variable on the dependent variable. 2) Indirect effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable with the existence of the intermediate variable. The indirect effect is

tested using the Sobel test, until the mean variable is determined for the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table 8: Result of the fourth hypothesis test

Dimension	Overall performance		
	Beta	T- Test	Sig.
Processes	0.206	2.074	0.041
HR	0.457	4.437	0.000
R	R Square	F Change	Sig. F Change
0.722	0.522	54.563	0.000
Effect Size Measurement			
	Effect Size	Test Value	Sig.
Total Effect	0.560	T	8.688
Direct Effect (c')	0.206	T	2.074
Indirect Effect (ab)	0.354	Sobel (z)	4.206
ab/c	0.632		
ab/c'	1.718		

The results indicated that the value of (F) of the model was (54.563), and the probability value (0.000) was a statistically significant value at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) indicating the significance of the model as a whole. The results revealed that the introduction of the human resource development standard in addition to the standard of operations (as independent variables) in the model led to an increase in the explanatory capacity of the model. The value of the coefficient of selection (52.2%) was 9.4% (20.6%), which is a statistically significant value at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), while the total effect was ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The indirect effect value (35.4%), which represents (63.2%) of the total effect, is a statistical function at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). In view of the direct and indirect impact of the impact, it is clear to the researcher that the criterion of interest in human resources partly mediates the relationship between adopting the standard of operations and improving the overall performance in Palestinian universities.

This finding was agreed with Calvo-Mora & Roldan (2006), which showed that leadership leads to the development of excellence in results across operations. And studies by: (Calvo-Mora & Roldán: 2006), (Adel, 2009), (Moradzadeh: 2015) which showed a significant relationship between processes and the results of university performance.

The relationship between processes and performance results is logical and natural. The more the university performs its operations distinctly, through: a clear methodology for designing and managing operations, improving its processes in creative ways that generate added value for students and beneficiaries, and design academic programs and services as needed by students, It is expected and expected that the performance results will be distinct, whether the outcomes of

students and beneficiaries, employees or society, and also at the level of overall performance results. The TQM approach is a holistic approach that focuses not only on outputs but on all stages of the system. Inputs, processes and outputs. This does not happen without a vital role of human forces in the implementation of operations efficiently and effectively to improve performance,

7. RESULTS

- There was a statistically significant effect at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the adoption of the standard of operations on improving the overall performance in Palestinian universities. The value of R Square (42.8%) indicates that 42.8% improvement in the overall performance is due to the adoption of the standard of operations in the universities under study.
- There was a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the adoption of the standard of operations on the development of human resources in the Palestinian universities "where the value of the coefficient of selection (R Square) (64.5%), indicating that (64.5%) of adopting the standard focus on the forces Humanity is due to the adoption by Palestinian universities of the standard of operations.
- There was a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for human resources to improve the overall performance of Palestinian universities. "The value of R (50.1%) indicates that (50.1%) improvement in overall performance is due to adopt the Palestinian universities to the standard of attention to human resources.

- There was a statistically significant effect at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the adoption of the standard of operations on improving the overall performance with the concern of human resources as an intermediate variable in the Palestinian universities. (Path Analysis), where some of the preconditions for testing the intermediate role of the variable, which is the significance of the tests for the three previous hypotheses, were checked. The tests were all statistically significant at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Increasing the focus of universities on human resources through the appropriate form to achieve the objectives of the university on the one hand, and workers on the other, and in line with the approach of quality and excellence.
- More attention to the management of operations by universities through the design and development of academic programs and internal services as needed by students, and to improve processes in innovative ways to generate added value for students and beneficiaries.
- The need for universities to plan and implement performance improvement projects for all standards, particularly the results criteria.
- The need for universities to invest this good performance in obtaining certificates of quality and excellence from international quality institutions, because it has a great impact on the reputation of the University, and gives the university momentum to continue the process of improvement and improvement of performance.

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